

Impact of Counselling Strategies on Educational Challenges among Single Parents' Children in Kogi Local Government Area, Kogi State.

Aina, Josephine Shola¹

jaina@noun.edu.ng, ainajshola@yahoo.com

08036093532

¹Department of Educational Foundations Faculty of Education, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria.

Abstract

The study examined the impact of counselling strategies on educational challenges among single parents' children in Kogi State. Five research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. Population of the study consists of all teachers in public secondary schools in Kogi Local Government Area during the 2023 / 2024 academic session. Random sampling method was used to select 15 public secondary schools and purposive sampling technique was employed in choosing 14 teachers from each school thereby constituting a total sample of 210 (male 65 and female 115) teachers. Questionnaire titled "Educational challenges of Single Parents' children Inventory" (ECSPCI) was used for data collection. Data gathered were analyzed with frequency distribution. Descriptive statistics was used to answer the research questions, one way ANOVA and the Independent sample test (IST) was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 significant levels. Findings of the study uncovered multiple causes of single parenting and there were several challenges facing them. Several behavioural traits changes were suggested to be adopted by single parents to ameliorate their challenges. The study revealed that there is no significant difference between male and female on the counselling strategies that address the educational challenges of single parents' children. Educational qualifications of respondents actually influence the counselling strategies that address the educational challenges of single parents' children. Conclusion was drawn and it was recommended that government, school proprietors and principals should provide annual professional development programs for school counsellors to be trained on modalities to handle challenges related to single parents' children.

Keywords: Educational, Challenges, parents, children, counselling, strategies

Introduction

The socialization of children is very important for the continuity of any culture. The family is said to be the most important agent of socialization, especially for children. Single parenthood is a reality that besieges many families irrespective of race, culture and nationality. Families with single mothers, especially experience a lot more challenges than a regular family including social isolation, economic difficulties and personal problems. The home, which is the traditional nuclear family, is the smallest unit and microcosm of the larger society. The home is the first environment within a family and an essential place in the upbringing of children. Therefore, the family is a universal union and it is hard to envisage how society can function properly without the family (Amede. and Aina, 2019). A child needs both her parents for proper nourishment and to inculcate strong basic moral, spiritual, social physical and cognitive principles in their children (Santrock, 2004). To this end, the child is morally, mentally upright and emotionally balanced when the caring responsibilities are carried out by both parents (Tenibiaje and Tenibiaje, 2011). It is unfortunate that most families today are divided, separated and unstable. Within single parent families, however, there is no sharing of the parental responsibilities; the one parent, whether mother or father, is doing all of the parenting responsibilities as an entity (Schadler, 2016). The family may be receiving supports from outsiders but the one parent serves as the single authority figure within the household. The incidences of single-parent families have increased in number with time. Today, single-parent families are quite common. As marriage rates continue to change, family structures continue to look different (McLanahan and Sawhill, 2015). Research suggests that the number of single parent families continue to increase, and of these families, the majority of the single parents are single mothers (Federal Interagency Forum on Child and Family Statistics, 2017). Nigeria, like other sub-Saharan countries, is experiencing a steady growth in out-of-wedlock motherhood, which resulted from marital instability, widowhood or personal choice. These have brought about a large number of single parent mothers catering for families across the country. Also, the 2014 United States Census Bureau report showed that there were no fewer than 12 million single parent families in the U.S, of which more than 83 percent were headed by women. A 2014 cross-sectional study indicated that no fewer than one million women aged 20 to 85 years were either divorced or separated from their husbands, while 1.7 million were widowed (Ovuorie, 2020).

Factors such as divorce, separation, death of parent, unintended pregnancy, or birth to unmarried couples and single parent adoption are the major causes of single parenthood in our society today (Amato and Patterson, 2017). Parental death due to disease and unnatural causes like accidents or suicides is the primary reason for a single mother raising her children. Children are increasingly socialized by influences outside the immediate family. As a result of poor parental care and guidance caused by divorce, separation or death of a partner, children are exposed to potentially damaging situation (Olaleye and Oladeji, 2010).

Being a mother is never an easy task, and being a single mother adds its own set of new challenges. Transitioning to a single-parent household can disrupt a child's routines, education, housing arrangement and family income. It can also intensify the incidence of parental conflict and stress. Single parent families affect both the child and the parent in many ways. When children are brought up by a single parent, it makes life more demanding and challenging on the parent. If this phase of the child's life is not well managed, it may lead to maladjustment in life. Akpeli (2018) opined that matrimonial separation commonly involves major emotional distress for child relationship. As such, about twice as many children from one parent families compared to two parent families drop out of school. Maurya and Parasar (2015) describe additional struggles of single parents as including, "expensive day care, shortage of quality time with children, balancing between work and home duties, and serious economic struggles are among seemingly endless problems that single parent families need to resolve" (p.1236).

The financial burden on single parent families is also colossal. Many children recognize the economic burdens of their parents, acknowledging that their parent has a tight budget and worries about money (Nixon, Greene, & Hogan, 2015). All of these stressors often lead to a hectic home environment where they are trying to raise their children. In addition to the challenges for basic needs that impact the dynamics of the family, there are often barriers that also sway parents' mental health. Added on to the plethora of other challenges, single parents are also less likely to receive social support (McArthur and Wink worth, 2017).

Parents can minimize these challenges by managing finance effectively, setting up a support system, maintaining a daily routine, being consistent with discipline. Single parents are often found using distorted or inconsistent behaviour management techniques with their child, causing more stress on both the child and the parent and leading to the unintentional reinforcement of the child's negative behaviours (Briggs, Cox, Sharkey, Briggs, & Black, 2016).

Many factors determine the educational performance of students. Learners need favourable environment to excel; they need textbooks, prompt payment of tuition fees, school uniform, adequate time and furniture to study, home instructors among others. Most of these are beyond the reach of many single parents. However, school counsellors can leverage on their training to ameliorate the educational challenges facing the children from a sole parents.

Numerous guidance and counselling services, including assessment, information, placement, orientation, evaluation, referral, and follow-up, are practice in schools (Aina, 2021). These significant guidance and counselling strategies can address the needs, difficulties, and issues of students. This study therefore examined how to address the educational challenges of single parents' children through counselling strategies.

Single parents and their children can face various challenges. Financial strains is a common issue, as single parents often have to support their families on a single income. Time management can also be difficult, as they juggle work, household responsibility, and child care. Children may also experience emotional difficulties such as felling different from their peers or missing the presence the other parent. Additionally, there can be societal stigma, educational challenges, lack of role model, or judgment towards single- parents' families, which can affect both the parent and the child. Providing support networks, access to, and open communication within the family can help mitigate these challenges. This study therefore examined impact of counselling strategies on educational challenges among single parents' children in Kogi Local Government Areas in the view to finding solution to the challenges.

Objectives of the study

The study examined how to address the educational challenges of single parents' children through counselling strategies. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Examine the causes of single parent families in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State.
2. Identify the challenges of single parent families in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State
3. Determine the recommended behavioural traits to be adopted by single parents to enable them to ameliorate these challenges.
4. Identify the educational implications of children under single parents
5. Verify the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children

6. Securitize the significantly influence of gender on the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parents' children.
7. Appraise the significantly influence of educational qualifications of respondents on the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parents' children.

Research Questions

1. What are the causes of single parent families in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State?
2. What are the challenges of single parent families in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State?
3. What are the recommended behavioural traits to be adopted by single parents to enable them to ameliorate their Challenges?
4. What are the educational implications of children under single parents?
5. What are the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children?

Hypotheses

1. H₁: Gender does not significantly influence the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children.
2. H₁: Educational qualifications of respondents do not significantly influence the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was descriptive survey design. The researcher opined that descriptive survey is best for this research work because it provides summaries about the sample and describes the basic features of the data in the study. The population of the study consists of all teachers in public secondary schools in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State during the 2023 / 2024 academic session. A total of 210 out of 400 public secondary schools teachers constituted the sample size for this study. Random samplings method was used to select 15 public secondary schools out of the available 16 were purposively sampled. Purposive sampling technique was employed in choosing 14 teachers from each school thereby constituting a total sample of 210 for the study (male 65 and female 115). This sample size is adequate because according to representative of the population and the findings from a study of that sample can be generalized for the population. Asika (1991) 10% element selected randomly from a population is to all intents and purposes deemed to be

Results

Research Question 1:

What are the causes of single parenting in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on the causes of single parenting.

S/N	Causes of single parenting:	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Q1	Divorce	180	543.00	3.0167	.46647	Accepted
Q2	Separation	180	551.00	3.0611	.43792	Accepted
Q3	Death of parent	180	544.00	3.0222	.48388	Accepted
Q4	Wrong choice of Partners	180	548.00	3.0444	.43354	Accepted
Q5	Lack of trust and suspicion	180	552.00	3.0667	.41749	Accepted
Q6	Single parent adoption	180	549.00	3.0500	.26479	Accepted
Q7	Wife battering	180	555.00	3.0833	.31490	Accepted
Q8	Barrenness	180	543.00	3.0167	.32537	Accepted
Q9	Adultery	180	545.00	3.0278	.32461	Accepted
Q10	In-law interference	180	548.00	3.0444	.52663	Accepted
	Total		5478	3.43	.39	Accepted

Table 1 revealed the descriptive Statistics on the causes of single parenting in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State. The total score is 5478, average Mean score of 3.43 and Standard Deviation of .39. The total average is 3.43 is above the weigh average of 2.5. The implication is that the causes of single parenting in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State are indeed multiple.

Research Question 2:

What are the challenges of single parenting in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State?

Table 2: Mean rating on the challenges of single parenting in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State

S/N	Challenges of single parent families	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Q11	Custody issues and cares. .	180	558.00	3.1000	.48555	Agreed
Q12	Parent has to single-handedly manage household chores and office work.	180	542.00	3.0111	.54914	Agreed
Q13	feeling the absence of another	180	540.00	3.0000	.58853	Agreed
Q14	Loneliness	180	556.00	3.0889	.48771	Agreed
Q15	The complete financial burden is put on a single parent.	180	525.00	2.9167	.65053	Agreed
Q16	Single-parent families have low self-esteem	180	531.00	2.9500	.56207	Agreed
Q17	society makes them feel guilty for being single	180	519.00	2.8833	.56207	Agreed
Q18	Depression and aggressive often overwhelm single parents which may affect children academic exercise	180	520.00	2.8889	.56814	Agreed
Q19	single parenting may exhibit poor leadership style may affect children academic activities	180	508.00	2.8222	.53016	Agreed
Q20	single parent families may experience psychological trauma that may affect children	180	508.00	2.8222	.68630	Agreed

Table 2 revealed the Mean rating on the challenges of single parent families in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State. Custody issues and cares top the list with a Mean average of 3.1000, followed by Loneliness. (3.0889), closely by Parent has to single-handedly manage household chores and office work with a Mean score of 3.0111. The total average is 2.94 is above the weigh average of 2.5. The implication is that there are several challenges facing single parent families in the area of study.

Research Question 3:

What are the recommended behavioural traits to be adopted by single parents to enable them ameliorate these challenges?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on the behavioral traits to be adopted by single parents to enable them ameliorate these challenges

S/N	Behavioural traits to be adopted by single parents	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
Q21	Setting up a support system	180	530.00	2.9444	.49265	Agreed
Q22	Effective managing of finance	180	551.00	3.0611	.33699	Agreed
Q23	Maintaining a daily routine	180	543.00	3.0167	.32537	Agreed
Q24	Being consistent with discipline	180	560.00	3.1111	.40787	Agreed
Q25	Answering questions honestly	180	531.00	2.9500	.59114	Agreed
Q26	Set clear rules, limits and boundaries	180	537.00	2.9833	.52294	Agreed
Q27	Spending time with children	180	556.00	3.0889	.43951	Agreed
Q28	Taking time off for oneself	180	520.00	2.8889	.56814	Agreed
Q29	Staying positive	180	532.00	2.9556	.51592	Agreed
Q30	Give students positive attention	180	548.00	3.0444	.42046	Agreed
			5408	3.00	..46	

Table 3 shows the descriptive Statistics on the behavioral traits to be adopted by single parents to enable them ameliorate the challenges. The total score is 5408, average Mean scores of 3.00 and Standard Deviation of .46. The total average which is 3.00 is above the weigh average of 2.5. The implication is that there are many behavioural traits to be adopted by single parents to enable them ameliorate the challenges.

Research Question 4:

What are the educational challenges of children under single parents?

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics on the Educational challenges of children under Single Parents

S/N	Educational implications of children under Single Parents	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
Q31	Hatred for a course and the lecturer.	180	597.00	3.32	.31266	Agreed
Q32	Depression hinders concentration	180	603.00	3.35	.42698	Agreed
Q33	Feeling of rejection affect class attendance	180	616.00	3.42	.22537	Agreed
Q34	Abandonment of academic pursuit	180	632.00	3.51	.30567	Agreed
Q35	Inferiority complex affects communication	180	594.00	3.30	.68444	Agreed
Q36	Fear and trauma instigates truancy	180	536.00	2.98	.44594	Agreed
Q37	Aggressive behaviours affects teaching and learning	180	513.00	2.85	.56814	Agreed
Q38	Low self-esteem diminishes class attention	180	639.00	3.55	.61544	Agreed
Q39	Withdrawn syndrome results in out of school	180	619.00	3.44	.34046	Agree
			5902	3.28	.42	

Table 4 shows the descriptive Statistics on the Educational Challenges of Children under Single Parenting in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State. The total score is 5902, average Mean scores of 3.28 and Standard Deviation of .42. The total average which is 3.28 is above the weigh average of 2.5. The implication is that the educational challenges of children under Single Parenting in the area of study are enormous.

Research Question 5:

What are the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of Single Parents' children?

Table 5: Mean rating on the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children

S/N	Counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
Q41	Individual counselling	180	543.00	3.0167	.42904	Agreed
Q42	Family counselling	180	561.00	3.1167	.33883	Agreed
Q43	Good Listening skill	180	555.00	3.0833	.34858	Agreed
Q44	Cognitive restructuring	180	559.00	3.1056	.35841	Agreed
Q45	Limits and boundaries will encourage your child to behave in positive ways	180	553.00	3.0722	.39594	Agreed
Q46	Set clear rules. Try to be consistent. Use routines	180	535.00	2.9722	.48933	Agreed
Q47	Rational emotive therapy	180	561.00	3.1167	.33883	Agreed
Q48	Group counselling	180	508.00	2.8222	.57075	Agreed
Q49	Family counselling	180	551.00	3.0611	.33699	Agreed
Q50	Career counselling	180	509.00	2.8278	.73864	Agreed
	Total		5435	3.02	.43	

Table 5 revealed the Mean rating on the counselling strategies that can address the Educational Challenges of Single Parents' Children. Family counselling top the list with a Mean average of 3.1167, followed by Cognitive restructuring (3.1056), closely by Good Listening skill with Mean scores of 3.0833. The total average is 3.02 and is above the weigh average of 2.5. The implication is that there are several counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1:

Gender does not significantly influence the counselling strategies in addressing the educational challenges of single parents' children.

Table 6: T-test analysis on the difference between male and female perception on the counselling strategies of educational challenges of single parents' children in Kogi L.G.A. of Kogi State

Group Statistics

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	dt	T	Sig.
Qualifications	Male	65	1.2923	.45836	.05685	178	-14.371	.186
	Female	115	2.3391	.47549	.04434			

At .05 significant level

The result in Table 6 shows that there is a significant difference between male and female on the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children at $t(-14.371)$, $df=178$, $P<.05$, with a Mean of 1.2923 for male and 2.3391 for female. The implication is that there is no significant difference between male and female on the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children.

Hypothesis 2: H_1 : Educational qualifications of respondents do not significantly influence the counselling strategies that will address the educational challenges of single parents' children.

Table 7: Descriptive statistic on the influence of educational qualifications of respondents on the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parents' children

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Uneducated	46	1	0	0	1	1	1	1
Educated	95	1.8	0.40212	0.04126	1.7181	1.8819	1	2
Semi Educated	39	2	0	0	2	2	2	2
Total	180	1.6389	0.48166	0.0359	1.568	1.7097	1	2

Table 7 above depicts a Descriptive statistic on the influence of educational qualifications of respondents on the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parents' children. The table gives categories of Certificate teachers into Uneducated, Educated and Semi Educated. A total of 180 respondents participated in the study. Out of this figure, 46 were Uneducated, 95 were Educated and 39 are Semi Educated. The Mean scores for the Uneducated, Educated and Semi Educated are 1.0000, 1.8000 and 2.0000 respectively; with a total Mean score of 1.6389.

Table 8: One-way ANOVA statistic on the influence of educational qualifications of respondents on the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parents' children

Gender	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	26.328	2	13.164	153.290	.000
Within Groups	15.200	177	.086		
Total	41.528	179			

The one-way statistics revealed a significant difference between and within groups as shown in Table 8 above with $F(153.290=)$ $df, 2/179$, $p = .000$. The hypothesis which states that Educational qualifications of respondents do not significantly influence the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parenting was therefore rejected. A posteriori in Table 4.12 was tested to determine the degree of differences between the categories of teachers' qualifications. The Mean differences for Uneducated are -.80000 and -1.00000 to Educated and Semi Educated respectively. Degrees are -.80000.51 and -.20000 to Uneducated and Semi Educated respectively while Semi Educated to Uneducated and Educated are and -1.00000 and -.20000 respectively. The implication is that educational qualifications of respondents do actually influence the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parents' children.

Table 9: Tukey HSD Multiple Comparisons on the influence of educational qualifications of respondents on the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parents' children

Tukey HSD

(I) Qualifications	(J) Qualifications	Mean Difference			95% Confidence Interval	
		(I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Uneducated	Educated	-.80000*	.05264	.000	-.9244	-.6756
	Semi Educated	-1.00000*	.06379	.000	-1.1508	-.8492
Educated	Uneducated	.80000*	.05264	.000	.6756	.9244
	Semi Educated	-.20000*	.05573	.001	-.3317	-.0683
Semi Educated	Uneducated	1.00000*	.06379	.000	.8492	1.1508
	Educated	.20000*	.05573	.001	.0683	.3317

*. The Mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Discussion of findings

Research questions sought to determine the causes of single parent families in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State. The finding revealed that the causes of single parent families in the Locality are indeed multiple. This agreed with Amato and Patterson (2017) who found that factors such as divorce, separation, death of parent, unintended pregnancy, or birth to unmarried couples and single parent adoption are the major causes of single parenthood in our society today. Parental death due to disease and unnatural causes like accidents or suicides is the primary reason for a single mother raising her children. Increasingly, divorce and separation are also the reasons for a growing number of single mothers. Children are increasingly socialized by influences outside the immediate family. As a result of poor parental care and guidance caused by divorce, separation or death of a partner, children are exposed to potentially damaging situation (Olaleye and Oladeji, 2010). The finding in research question 2 showed that there are several challenges facing single parent families in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State. It agreed with Maurya and Parasar (2015) who describe additional struggles of single parents as including, “expensive day care, shortage of quality time with children, balancing between work and home duties, and linked economic struggles are among seemingly endless problems that single parent families need to resolve” (p.1236). The financial burden on single parent families is also immense. Many children recognize the financial burdens of their parents, acknowledging that their parent has a tight budget and worries about money (Nixon, Greene, and Hogan, 2015). Within single parent families, however, there is no sharing of the parental responsibilities; the one parent, whether mother or father, is doing all of the parenting as a single entity (Schadler, 2016).

Research question 3 revealed that there are many recommended behavioral traits to be adopted by single parents to enable them to ameliorate their challenges. Single parents are often found using distorted or inconsistent behaviour management techniques with their child, causing more stress on both the child and the parent and leading to the unintentional reinforcement of the child’s negative behaviours (Briggs, Cox, Sharkey, Briggs, & Black, 2016).

Research Question 4 sought to scrutinize the educational implications of children under single parents. The finding revealed that educational implications of children under single parents in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State are enormous. This concurred with Akpeli (2018) who opined that separation commonly involves major emotional distress for child/parent relationship. As such, about twice as many children from one parent families compared to two parent families drop out of school.

The analysis of Research Question 5 revealed several counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents’ children. Guidance and counselling services, including assessment, information, placement, orientation, evaluation, referral, and follow-up, are offered (Aina, 2021). With its respective services, each of these significant guidance and counselling components addresses the needs, difficulties, and issues of students.

Conclusion

The outcome of the study uncovers the causes of single parent families among the respondents as being multiple. There are many behavioral traits to be adopted by single parents. The Educational challenges are also enormous. Several counselling strategies were employed to address the Educational challenges. There was no significant difference between male and female on the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents’ children. Educational qualifications of respondents do actually influence the counselling strategies that will address the educational challenges of single parents’ children

Recommendations

1. Government, school proprietors and principals should provide enabling environment for the teachers to teach students with varying family backgrounds.
2. Government, school proprietors and principals should establish strict rules and regulations to guide students' conducts.
3. Government should provide annual professional development for school counsellors to be adequately trained on modalities to handle challenges related to single parents' children.
4. There is an urgent need by government to engage the services of trained school counsellors to deal with the challenges related to single parents' children.

Implication for Counselling

The study examined the educational challenges of single parents' children through counselling strategies. It would help school counsellors to discover some of the reasons why single parents' children behave disorderly without courtesy and help them access the root causes of educational challenges in public secondary schools with a view to provide solutions. Its outcome would help school counsellors to assist parents, teachers and governments to find out effective counselling strategies to address the challenges facing single parents.

References

- Akpeli, A.O. (2018). *Building positive relationships with children as a single parent*. Punch Newspaper, 13 September, 2018
- Amato, P. R., & Patterson, S. E. (2017). Single-parent households and mortality among children and youth. *Social Science Research*, 63, 253-262. doi: 10.1016/j.ssresearch.2016.09.017
- Aina, J.S. (2021). Counselling Services and Academic Performance of Students in National Open University of Nigeria. *NOUN Journal of Education*. 7. 17-30.
- Amede, L. & Aina, J. S. (2019). Influence of parental socio-economic status on students educational achievements in Nigeria, *Nigerian Journal of Sociology of Education (NJSE)*, 13(1 & 2): 251 – 263.
- Briggs, H. E., Cox, W. H., Sharkey, C. N., Briggs, A. C., & Black, M. (2016). A review of the research on Pinkston's single-parent group training program. *Research on Social Work Practice*, 26(1), 128-144.
- Asika, N. (1991). *Research methodology in behavioural sciences*. Lagos: Longman, Nigeria Plc.
- Briggs, H. E., Cox, W., Sharkey, C. N., Corley, N., Briggs, A. C., & Black, M. (2016). The role of behavioural theory in model development research with single parent families. *Children & Adolescent Social Work Journal*, 33(4), 349-363.
- Federal Interagency Forum on Child and Family Statistics (2017). America's children: Key national indicators of well-being. Retrieved from https://www.childstats.gov/pdf/ac2017/ac_17.pdf
- Haine-Schlagel, R. & Walsh, N. E. (2015). A review of parent participation engagement in child and family mental health treatment. *Clinical Child and Family Psychology Review*, 18(2), 133-150.
- Maurya A. K., & Parasar, A. (2015). The effect of single parent and both parents family on emotional and behavioral problems. *Indian Journal of Health and Wellbeing*, 6(12), 1235-1237. Retrieved from: http://www.iahrw.com/index.php/home/journal_detail/19#list
- McArthur, M., & Winkworth, G. (2017). What do we know about the social networks of single parents who do not use supportive services? *Child & Family Social Work*, 22(2), 638- 647.
- McLanahan, S., & Sawhill, I. (2015). Marriage and child wellbeing revisited: Introducing the issue. *The Future of Children*, 25(2), 3-9.
- Motamedi, F., Ghobari-Bonab, B., Beh-pajooh, A., Yekta, M. S., & Afrooz, G. A. (2016). Developing an emotional intelligence program training and study its effectiveness on emotional intelligence of adolescents with emotional and behavioral problems that living in a single parent families. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 6(2), 101-110.
- Nixon, E., Greene, S., & Hogan, D. (2015). "It's what's normal for me": Children's experiences of growing up in a continuously single-parent household. *Journal of Family Issues* 36(8),
- Olaleye, Y.L, & Oladeji, D. (2010) "Single Parenthood Impact on Street Children in Ibadan
- Ovuorie, T. (2020). *The challenge of single mothers in Nigeria (Part 2)*. Available at: <https://humanglemedia.com/the-challenge-of-single-mothers-in-nigeria-part-2/>
- Porter, L. S., & Keefe, F. J. (2017). Couple-based communication interventions for cancer: moving beyond a 'one size fits all' approach. *Acta Oncologica Foundation*, 57(5), 693- 695.

- Richter, D. & Lemola, S. (2017). Growing up with a single mother and life satisfaction in adulthood: A test of mediating and moderating factors. *PLoS ONE*, 12(6), 1-15. doi: 10.1371/
- Santrock, J. W., (2004) “*Life-Span Development*” (9th Ed.) McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc. New York.
- Schadler, C. (2016). How to define situated and ever-transforming family configurations? A new materialist approach. *Journal of Family Theory*, 8(4), 503-514. doi: 10.1111/jftr.12167
- Stack, R. J. & Meredith, A. (2017). The impact of financial hardship on single parents: An exploration of the journey from social distress to seeking help. *Journal of Family Economic Issues*, 39(2), 233-242. doi: 10
- Tenibiaje, D. J., (2011) “Effect of Single Parenthood on the Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Ekiti State, Nigeria: *International Review of Social Sciences and Humanities*. 2. (1). pp 240-248